

SYNTHESIS OF SUBSTITUTED DINITROPHENYL KETONES AND PHENYLACETIC ACIDS. PART I.

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2:4-Dinitro-6-bromophenylacetone and 2:4-dinitro-6-bromophenylacetic acid have been prepared by the ketonic and acid hydrolysis respectively of the product obtained by the condensation of 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-bromobenzene with ethyl acetoacetate. The ketone has been characterised by the preparation of suitable derivatives. The reduction of 2:4-dinitro-6-bromophenylacetic ester by tin and hydrochloric acid gave rise to an indole derivative.

The simple aromatic halogen compounds like chlorobenzene, do not react with the monosodium derivatives of acetoacetic or malonic ester, as the halogen atom in this case is very firmly fixed to the nucleus. The introduction of negative groups (like nitro), specially in the *ortho* and *para* positions to the halogen atom, however, makes it extremely labile and thus facilitates its replacement by various groups. Such compounds can also be condensed with acetoacetic or malonic ester. Considerable work has been done on this subject, the more important contributions being those of Richter (*Ber.*, 1888, 21, 2473), Heckmann (*Annalen*, 1884, 220, 137), Jackson (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1232), Reissert and Heller (*Ber.*, 1904, 37, 4634), Borsche (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 601), Hantzsch and Picton (*Ber.*, 1909, 42, 2126), Borsche and Rantschaff (*Annalen*, 1911, 379, 180), Borsche Bahr (*ibid.*, 1914, 402, 91), and Dey and Doraiswami (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 309).

The esters obtained as above by the condensation of the polynitro halogen compounds with acetoacetic or malonic ester also undergo ketonic and acid hydrolysis and thus provide a suitable method for the preparation of substituted phenylketones and phenylacetic acids.

In the present paper this reaction has been extended to 1-chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-bromobenzene with the object of obtaining the appropriate phenylacetone (which has been further characterised by the preparation of the phenylhydrazone and oxime) and phenylacetic acid. The reduction of 2:4-dinitro-6-bromophenylacetoacetic ester by tin and hydrochloric acid, which yields an indole derivative, has also been carried out during the course of the work.

EXPERIMENTAL

2:4-Dinitro-6-bromophenylacetoacetic Ester.—The monosodium derivative of acetoacetic ester was prepared as usual from sodium tape (3.5 g., 0.15 mole) and ethyl acetoacetate (19.5 g., 0.15 mole), dissolved in 50 c.c. of dry ether, in a flask fitted with a reflux condenser and a mechanical

stirrer. 1-Chloro-2:4-dinitro-6-bromobenzene (21.1 g, 0.075 mole) (Sane and Joshi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 459) was then added under ice-cooling and the mixture refluxed for 6 hours. Next day the reaction mixture was shaken twice with 100 c.c. of water and then once with 100 c.c. of 1% caustic soda solution. The combined extracts were acidified with dilute nitric acid, when a red oil separated. The aqueous portion was decanted off, the oil redissolved in 1% caustic soda solution and extracted with ether to remove any unreacted acetoacetic ester. It was then reprecipitated with dilute nitric acid, dissolved in cold alcohol and left over for slow evaporation. After a week's standing, dark red crystals separated, which were filtered and dried. Further evaporation of the filtrate yielded a semisolid mass. The crystalline product for purification was redissolved in alcohol, filtered and left for evaporation, when brown-red needles were obtained, m.p. 73-74°, yield 24.7 g. (88% of theory). (Found: N, 7.36. $C_{12}H_{11}O_7N_2Br$ requires N, 7.47 per cent).

2:4-Dinitro-6-bromophenylacetone was obtained by dissolving the finely powdered ester (2.5 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (25 c.c.) to which 7 c.c. of water were then added under constant stirring. This resulted in the evolution of carbon dioxide and when this ceased to evolve, the clear brown solution was poured on crushed ice. The raw ketone, which separated as a semisolid mass, was left overnight in a frigidaire and then filtered. This was then dissolved in alcohol and left over for slow evaporation. The crystals which separated were further purified by dissolving in hot alcohol, filtering and leaving the filtrate to evaporate when fine brown needles of m.p. 111-12° were obtained in quantitative yield (2g.). (Found: N, 9.42. $C_9H_7O_5N_2Br$ requires N, 9.24 per cent).

The *oxime* was prepared by dissolving the above ketone (1g.) in alcohol and adding to it hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.5 g.) followed by caustic soda solution till it turned just alkaline to phenolphthalein. After refluxing the mixture for 1 hour, the contents were cooled and poured in 100 c.c. of water when a colloidal suspension was obtained. This was allowed to stand overnight in the frigidaire and then left to settle at room temperature for a week after which it was filtered and purified by washing it with boiling alcohol; the blackish brown product did not melt, yield 0.6 g. (60% of theory). (Found: N, 13.81. $C_9H_8O_5N_3Br$ requires N, 13.20 per cent).

The *phenylhydrazone* was obtained by dissolving the ketone (0.5 g.) in minimum quantity of alcohol and adding to it about 8 drops of phenylhydrazine. The mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 15 minutes, and cooled; the phenylhydrazone separating was then filtered, washed with a little alcohol and recrystallised from hot alcohol, m.p. 127°, yield 0.65 g. (quantitative). (Found: N, 14.30. $C_{15}H_{13}O_4N_4$ Br requires N, 11.25 per cent).

2:4-Dinitro-6-bromophenylacetic Acid.—The ester (1 g.) was refluxed for half an hour with 20% alcoholic potash (4.5 c.c.) to which a few drops of water had been added. The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid.

The alcohol was distilled off and the solution allowed to cool and stand overnight. The product which separated out was filtered at the pump and washed several times with cold alcohol to remove the unchanged dinitro-bromophenylacetoacetic ester, leaving the pure brown-black acid. It was recrystallised by dissolving in hot alcohol, filtering and allowing the filtrate to evaporate, m.p. 184°, yield 0.5 g. (quantitative). (Found : N, 8.76. $C_8H_5O_2N_2Br$ requires N, 9.18 per cent).

2-Methyl-3-ethylcarboxy-5-bromo-7-aminoindole.—2:4-Dinitro-6-bromophenyl-acetoacetic ester (2.5 g.) was dissolved in alcohol (15 c.c.) on a water-bath and a mixture of 2.5 c.c. of stannous chloride solution and 6 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid was added. The dark brown solution was warmed for a few minutes and then cooled under brisk stirring. Excess of granulated tin was then added and the solution refluxed for 3 hours on a water-bath. End of the reaction was tested by treating a drop of the reaction mixture with NaOH, when no strong colour was developed and the free indole derivative got precipitated in microscopic form. The refluxed solution was filtered hot from excess of tin, and the alcohol evaporated from the filtrate, when the tin double salt separated out. Hydrochloric acid was added to dissolve the precipitate as much as possible and the solution filtered. The tin was precipitated completely from the filtrate by hydrogen sulphide. The solution obtained containing the hydrochloride of the amine was neutralised with ammonia, when a white, heavy and flocculent precipitate was obtained, which turned black on exposure to air.

The product after repeated crystallisation from hot alcohol gave a dark coloured crystalline substance which did not melt. (Found : N, 9.92. $C_{12}H_{13}O_2N_2$ Br requires N, 9.45 per cent).

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